

Synthesis and spectral characterization of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of dioxadiazamacrocycles derived from α -diketones and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane

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Abstract : Chromium(III) and iron(III) complexes of the type $[ML(NO_3)_2]NO_3$ (where $M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}$, $L = 12$ -membered macrocycle having N_2O_2 donor set) have been synthesized by cyclocondensation of 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane with α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione and benzil in the presence of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} . The antibacterial activities of the complexes as growth inhibiting agents, have been carried out against several species of bacteria.

Keywords : Chromium(III), iron(III), α -diketone.

Due to the resemblance of macrocyclic complexes with biomolecules they are used in identification of diseases and normal tissues¹. In particular, the macrocycles with mixed oxygen-nitrogen donor atoms are used as sensors for cations, anions and molecular scaffolds for materials and biological models²⁻⁶. Oxa-azamacrocycles are also efficient complexing agents for a variety of transition and heavy metal cations⁷⁻⁹. We report herein the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of N_2O_2 macrocycles derived from 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione or benzil.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} nitrates with 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and different α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione and benzil in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocycles (Scheme 1).

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids which are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide etc. but soluble in dimethylsulphoxide and partially soluble in dichloromethane. These are stable at room temperature but decompose at higher temperatures. The elemental analyses of the complexes confirm their stoichiometry (Table 1).

	M	R ¹	R ²
(1a) Cr	(1b) Fe	CH ₃	CH ₃
(2a) Cr	(2b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅
(3a) Cr	(3b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇
(4a) Cr	(4b) Fe	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅
(5a) Cr	(5b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅
(6a) Cr	(6b) Fe	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

Magnetic moments : The magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 1. The μ_{eff} values for Cr^{III} complexes are in the range 3.89–4.14 B.M., which correspond to three unpaired electrons¹⁰. The μ_{eff} values for

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of the macrocyclic complexes

Compds.	Complexes	Colour (Yield %)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				Metal	N		
1a	[Cr{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (58)	220	11.77 (11.90)	6.29 (6.42)	4.02	114
2a	[Cr{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (44)	232	11.62 (11.54)	6.02 (6.22)	4.14	106
3a	[Cr{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (48)	198	11.36 (11.19)	5.97 (6.03)	3.89	118
4a	[Cr{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (52)	215	11.05 (11.19)	5.93 (6.03)	3.91	105
5a	[Cr{(Ph)(Me)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (57)	265	10.47 (10.43)	5.40 (5.62)	4.06	121
6a	[Cr{(Ph) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (56)	234	9.15 (9.26)	4.75 (4.99)	4.10	109
1b	[Fe{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (80)	185	12.74 (12.69)	6.15 (6.36)	5.99	105
2b	[Fe{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (72)	201	12.31 (12.29)	6.07 (6.16)	6.02	99
3b	[Fe{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (61)	175	11.75 (11.93)	5.73 (5.98)	6.10	114
4b	[Fe{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (62)	210	12.09 (11.93)	5.83 (5.98)	5.72	119
5b	[Fe{(Me)(Ph)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (37)	190	11.02 (11.12)	5.37 (5.57)	5.97	122
6b	[Fe{(Ph) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (50)	198	10.01 (9.89)	4.86 (4.96)	6.13	107

the Fe^{III} complexes are in the range 5.72–6.13 B.M. which are consistent with high spin d^5 system as observed earlier^{11,12}.

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of the macrocyclic complexes are given in Table 1. For Fe^{III} complexes molar conductances in DMSO are in the range 99–122 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which are typical of 3 : 1 electrolytes. Thus the complexes appear to be hexacoordinated. Hexacoordinated Fe^{III} complexes of the macrocycle 2,13-dimethyl-3,6,9,12,18-pentaazabicyclo[12.3.1]octadecan-1(18),2,12,14,16-pentaene have been reported¹³. For Cr^{III} complexes molar conductances are in the range 105–121 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ corresponding to 3 : 1 electrolyte¹⁴ suggesting that the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes of macrocycles show three bands in the region 16900–17500, 23325–25440 and 26550–28980 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹⁴. The positions of these bands

are consistent with distorted octahedral geometry of chromium(III) complexes.

Electronic spectra of Fe^{III} complexes of oxazamacrocycles show three bands. The band at $\sim 13555 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transition. Absorption bands in the region $\sim 16900\text{--}17000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transitions. Intense ligand to metal charge transfer bands appear in the region $\sim 28000\text{--}30506 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For Fe^{III} complexes of a macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, Rana *et al.*¹⁵ reported bands at $\sim 17500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and at $\sim 25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions. For Fe^{III} complexes of a macrocycle derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane the charge transfer bands have been reported at $\sim 30000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ⁸.

IR spectra : None of the spectra exhibits absorption bands at 1700 and 3200–3400 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to unreacted keto or primary amine group. In the mononuclear Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of an

Table 2. *m/z* values and % relative intensities of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of macrocycles

Sl. no.	Fragment	Compd.	[Cr{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃)NO ₃]	[Cr{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	[Fe{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	[Fe{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃
1.	[M] ⁺		436 (33.3%)	464 (2.10%)	454 (1.7%)	468 (11.11%)
2.	[M-3NO ₃] ⁺		250 (1.8%)	278 (3.5%)	268 (1.4%)	282 (2.1%)
3.	[L] ⁺		198 (27%)	226 (5.2%)	212 (7.0%)	226 (14.28%)
4.	[L-CH ₃] ⁺		183 (2.7%)	211 (7.0%)	197 (4.2%)	211 (5.7%)
5.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	197 (5.2%)	183 (5.2%)	197 (5.1%)
6.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	183 (11.5%)	-	-
7.	[L-CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₃] ⁺		-	-	168 (4.2%)	182 (4.2%)
8.	[L-2CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	-	-	198 (4.2%)
9.	[L-2CH ₃] ⁺		168 (2.7%)	-	-	-
10.	[M-3NO ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺		235 (5.5%)	263 (1.7%)	253 (1.7%)	267 (2.8%)
11.	[M-3NO ₃ -CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	249 (1.7%)	239 (1.8%)	253 (4.5%)
12.	[M-3NO ₃ -CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	235 (3.5%)	-	-
13.	[M-3NO ₃ -CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₃] ⁺		-	-	224 (5.2%)	238 (11.4%)
14.	[M-3NO ₃ -2CH ₃ -CH ₂] ⁺		-	220 (3.5%)	-	224 (5.7%)
15.	[M-3NO ₃ -2CH ₃] ⁺		220 (5.8%)	-	-	-

N₆O₄ macrocycle⁹ derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 2-methoxyethylamine and Fe^{III}, Fe^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of a 15-membered N₃O₂ macrocycle⁸ derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane absence of absorption bands at 1700 and 3100–3300 cm⁻¹ which could be attributed to the unreacted carbonyl or primary amine groups has been reported. For Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of a macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, no absorption bands were detected at 1700 or 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to the residual keto or amine groups¹⁶.

All the complexes show a medium intensity absorption band in the region 1580–1630 cm⁻¹ assigned to the coordinated >C=N group. For macrocyclic complexes of dibenzotetraazamacrocycle derived from *o*-phenylenediamine and various diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione, benzil and benzoin, Malik and coworkers¹⁷ have reported $\nu_{C=N}$ at ~1650 cm⁻¹. In the IR spectra of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of macrocycle derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine absorption bands at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ ¹⁴. In cobalt(II) complexes of N₂O₂ macrocycle derived from salicylaldehyde and 5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzophenone bands at 1570–1650 cm⁻¹ have been reported due to $\nu_{C=N}$ ¹⁸.

A band at 1015–1040 cm⁻¹ in all the macrocyclic complexes can be assigned to coordinated nitrate and the appearance of bands at 1460–1560 cm⁻¹ confirms the unidentate coordination mode of the nitrate groups¹⁹. In Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of a macrocycle derived from 2,3-butanedione and 2,6-diaminopyridine absorption bands at 1265, 1010 and 860 cm⁻¹ have been reported for unidentate coordinated nitrate groups¹². All the macrocyclic complexes exhibit absorption bands in the region 1350–1380 and 820–840 cm⁻¹ attributed to free nitrate. In Cr^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes, absorption bands at ~1350, 1230 and 825 cm⁻¹ are due to ionic nitrate¹⁵. In lanthanide(III) complexes of a macrocycle derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,2-diaminobenzene absorption bands at 1000–1010, 1280–1300, 1340–1440 and 1470–1514 cm⁻¹ have been reported for unidentate coordinated nitrate²⁰. A new band in the region 340–480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of chromium(III) complexes can be assigned to $\nu(\text{Cr-O})$ ⁷.

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of the complexes [Cr{(Me)₂[12]dieneN₂O₂}(NO₃)₂]NO₃, Cr{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN₂O₂}(NO₃)₂]NO₃, [Fe{(Me)-(Et)[12]dieneN₂O₂}(NO₃)₂]NO₃ and [Fe{(Et)₂[12]-

dieneN₂O₂}(NO₃)₂]NO₃ have been recorded using NBA matrix. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. The complexes show the peaks corresponding to molecular ion [M⁺] and free macrocycle [L⁺] which confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. Cook *et al.*²¹ observed the peak corresponding to the macrocycle in the mass spectra of the alkaline earth metal complexes of the macrocycle derived from furan-2,5-dicarbaldehyde and 3,6,9-trioxaundecane-1,11-diamine. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycle and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern for [Cr{(Me)₂[12]dieneN₂O₂}(NO₃)₂]NO₃ is given in Scheme 2. The complex exhibits a molecular ion [M⁺] peak at *m/z* 436 (33.3%). Fragment **b** is formed due to the loss of three nitrates from the molecular ion **a** and appears at *m/z* 250 (1.8%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

- [A] In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of CH₃ groups from **b** gives peaks at *m/z* 235 (5.5%) and *m/z* 220 (5.8%) due to the species **c** and **d** respectively. Loss of chromium atom from the species **d** finally gives the species **g** at *m/z* 168 (2.7%).
- [B] In this pathway the metal ion may be lost from the macrocycle in the beginning and a peak at *m/z* 198 (27%) appears due to the free macrocycle **e**. Subsequent loss of CH₃ groups from the macrocycle gives peaks at *m/z* 183 (2.7%) and 168 (2.7%) due to the species **f** and **g** respectively²².

Antibacterial activities : The data for the antibacterial activities of the compounds against various bacteria have been recorded in Table 3. The results point out that the compounds are inhibiting the growth of bacteria to a greater extent²³. Mode of action of antimicrobials may involve various targets in microorganisms, e.g. interference with the cell wall synthesis, damage to the cytoplasmic membrane as a result of which cell permeability may be altered or they may disorganize the lipoprotein leading to the cell death. According to Lawrence *et al.*²⁴ the variation in toxicity of different antibacterial agents against different organisms depends on impermeability of the cell. Such activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and Tweedy's chelation theory²⁵. According to Overtone's concept of cell permeability, the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favours the passage of only lipid soluble material due to liposolubility, which is an important factor that controls

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Cr}\{(\text{Me}_2)[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$.

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of the complexes

Compds.	Inhibition (mm) after 24 h (conc. in ppm)		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (-)	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> (-)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (-)
1a	9	13	18
2a	11	9	12
3a	8	5	10
4a	7	7	13
5a	15	16	14
6a	11	13	9
1b	12	8	7
2b	8	3	6
3b	9	11	13
4b	6	9	8
5b	10	8	18
6b	15	7	9

antibacterial activity. On chelation, the polarity of the metal ion is reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbitals and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with the donor group. Further, it

increases the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring and enhances the penetration of the complexes into lipid membranes and blocks metal binding sites on the enzymes of the microorganism²⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were as supplied and the liquid ones were distilled before use.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : To the butanolic solution of Cr^{III} nitrate (0.890 g, 2.0 mmol in 15 ml *n*-butanol), a solution of 2,3-butanedione (0.191 g, 2.0 mmol in ~ 15 ml *n*-butanol) was added followed by a solution of 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane (0.329 g, 2.0 mmol in *n*-butanol) dropwise with constant stirring. A solid appeared during the addition and the stirring was continued for ~ 5 h maintaining the temperature at 60–70 °C. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly the corresponding Fe^{III} complex was synthesized. Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of the macrocycles derived from 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil were

also synthesized in a similar manner.

Cr and Fe were determined by standard methods²⁷. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (298 K) on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. Electronic spectra of the complexes (in DMSO) were recorded in the region 200–900 nm on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Antibacterial screening : Antibacterial activity was evaluated by the paper disc plate method²⁸. The nutrient agar medium (peptone, beef extract, NaCl and agar-agar) and 5 mm diameter paper discs of Whatmann No. 1 filter paper were used. The compounds were dissolved in 500 ppm concentration. The filter paper discs were soaked in different solutions of the compounds, dried and then placed in the petriplates previously seeded with the test organisms. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 30 °C and the inhibition zone around each disc was measured.

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